

BIOACTIVE GLASS-CERAMIC NANOPARTICLES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW SMART AND BIOMIMETIC COMPOSITE BIOMATERIALS

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SUMMARY

Bioactive glass-ceramic nanoparticles (nBGC) may be produced using sol-gel methodologies. These nanobiomaterials may be used in a series of biomedical applications, such as tissue engineering of mineralised tissues. The preparation of nBGC and their properties are resumed. Example of applicability of nBGC in the orthopaedic field are presented, including in the preparation of scaffolds based on nanocomposites, bioactive and biodegradable injectable systems or osteoconductive coatings.

Keywords: *Tissue Engineering, bioactive coatings and films, nanocomposites, nanoparticles.*

INTRODUCTION

It would be desirable to prepare synthetic bone analogues that would match both the chemical and mechanical properties of bone. Such a material should be bioresorbable to allow for the body's own tissue repair processes to regenerate natural bone. As obvious choice of materials for such a synthetic material could involve the combination of polymers and inorganic elements. For the particular case of tissue engineering applications, such composites are processes as porous structures or as hydrogel systems able to maintain the viability of encapsulated cells; such scaffolds should exhibit sufficient mechanical stability, adequate degradation profile, and should allow cellular attachment and proliferation towards new tissue formation.

In the case of orthopedic applications, the bone-bonding ability of a biomaterial is a very important property for bone tissue regeneration/replacement applications. Hench *et al.* [1,2] showed for the first time that some glasses, which contain SiO₂, Na₂O, CaO and P₂O₅ in specific proportions, spontaneously bond to living bone. Since then, many bioactive glasses such as Bioglass® [1,2], bioactive glass ceramics such as Ceravital® [3], A-W glass-ceramic [4,5], or dense calcium phosphate ceramics such as synthetic hydroxyapatite (HA) [6,7] have been used clinically with

bone-bonding ability. They have been developed in the forms of bulks or particulates with dense or porous structures. For example, Bioglass[®] in the form of particulates has been extensively used in periodontal bone repair [8]. HA, in bulk and granular forms with dense and porous structures, is currently used as bone spacers and fillers [9]. A-W Glass-ceramic has been applied, not only as bone spacer and filler in the bulk and granular forms, but also as artificial vertebrae, intervertebral discs, and iliac crests in dense bulk form [5]. Bioactive glasses have also been found to support enzyme activity [10,11], vascularization [12,13], foster osteoblast adhesion, and growth, and differentiation and induce the differentiation of mesenchymal cells into osteoblasts [14,15], which are extremely important aspects regarding tissue engineering applications. Particularly relevant for the development of bone tissue engineering was the finding that the dissolution products from bioactive glasses, in particular the 45S5 Bioglass[®] composition, upregulate the gene expression that control osteogenesis and the production of growth factors [16]. However, even A-W glass-ceramic, which has higher mechanical strength than the other bioactive ceramics and human cortical bone, cannot be used to repair bone defects in high-load bones, such as femoral and tibial bones, as its fracture toughness is lower and its elastic modulus is higher than those of cortical bone. In this work the emphasis will be given to bioactive glasses. Compared with HA, bioactive glass-ceramics exhibit a higher biomineralization capability *in vitro* because they exhibit a stronger dissolution rate; such behaviour is reflected *in vivo* [17].

Bioactive particles have been processed with different sizes. In some cases, that will be discussed later, it is desirable to use particles with nanosizes. For example, Bioglass[®]-based composites showed improved mechanical properties and higher protein adsorption capability when the inorganic nanoparticles are used instead of microparticles [18].

BIOACTIVITY

Bioactive ceramics or glasses spontaneously form chemical and mechanical strong bonds with bone through a biologically active hydroxycarbonated apatite layer formed at their surface, which is chemically and structurally similar to the mineral phase of bone when they are implanted [1,4,5, 19]. Such type of calcium phosphate (Ca-P) layer is not observed around materials that are not bioactive, demonstrating that this biologically active bone-like apatite layer is a prerequisite for the bonding between an artificial material and living bone [20]. Ca-P may be integrated into hydrophilic polymeric templates by alternate immersion in solutions containing calcium and phosphate ions. For example, it was possible to produce bioactive poly(L-lactic acid)-chitosan hybrid scaffolds by in-situ calcification of the polysaccharide component using such methodology [21]. Such pre-calcification procedures constitute a route to promote bioactivity in non-osteoconductive materials.

The analysis of the bioactivity of artificial materials when implanted *in vivo* has been reproduced *in vitro* by immersion experiments using a simulated physiological solution that mimics the typical ion concentrations in body fluids [22]. To understand what is the mechanism of apatite formation in bioactive materials, Kokubo et al. [32,23] proposed a protein-free and acellular simulated body fluid (SBF) with pH 7.4 and ionic composition (Na^+ 142.0, K^+ 5.0, Ca^{2+} 2.5, Mg^{2+} 1.5, Cl^- 147.8, HCO_3^- 4.2, HPO_4^{2-} 1.0, SO_4^{2-} 0.5 mM) nearly equal to those of the human blood plasma.

It is known that each surface-active ceramic has its own characteristics regarding the formation of the apatite layer. For example, when Bioglass[®] is soaked in SBF the first reaction of this type of bioactive glass surface is ion exchange, in which Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ in the glass exchange with H₃O⁺ in the solution, resulting in a pH increase of the solution as well as in the formation of a hydrated silica gel layer [24]. The formation of this hydrated silica gel layer at the surface of Bioglass[®], which is abundant in silanol (Si–OH) groups, provides favorable sites for the calcium phosphate nucleation [25,26]. Furthermore, the water molecules in SBF react with the Si–O–Si bond to form additional Si–OH groups [27]. Then, these functional groups induce apatite nucleation, and the released Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ ions accelerate apatite nucleation by increasing the ionic activity product (IAP) of apatite in the fluid. Tanashi and co-workers [28] have also reported that Si–OH groups were effective in apatite nucleation. Therefore, the mineralization induced by bioactive ceramics is due to the formation of specific surface functional groups such as Si–OH, which serve as effective sites for heterogeneous nucleation of Ca–P [29]. Additionally, an increase of IAP in the surrounding fluid could thereby promote the Ca–P nucleation and growth at the surface of bioactive ceramics [29]. Other functional groups besides Si–OH groups have been shown to induce bone-like apatite formation, namely Ti–OH, Zr–OH, Nb–OH, Ta–OH, –COOH, and PO₄H₂ [27]. All these functional groups have isoelectric zero points at pH values much lower than 7 and, thus, are negatively charged in the living body [30], inducing apatite formation through formations of an amorphous calcium compound, e.g., calcium silicate, calcium titanate, and the subsequent formation of an amorphous calcium phosphate [27]. This calcium phosphate spontaneously transforms into apatite, the stable phase in body environment [31].

NANOCOMPOSITES

Recent works about nanoglasses/nanoceramics and nanostructured biocomposites have shown that these materials provide alternatives not yet fully explored for orthopaedic applications [32], presenting improved mechanical and biocompatibility properties and exhibiting, in some extent, a micro- and nanoarchitecture similar to bone [33]. When compared with conventional ceramics or glass micro- or macro-particles, the use of nano-sized particles may have advantages in bone repair or regeneration, because it has been shown that the decrease of grain size allows the up-regulation in cellular adhesion, enhances osteoblast proliferation and differentiation and the biomineralization process is also enhanced [32]. Moreover, the use of bioactive nanoparticles may have intrinsic sense in the design of materials for biomedical applications. Figure 1 shows the possibility of using nanoparticles in the fabrication of materials, organised according to the dimension of the material: fibers (1D); surfaces (2D); and porous and other 3D systems.

The combination of a polymeric matrix and bioactive nanoparticles may be used to produce nanocomposites composed by nanofibers (Fig. 1a). For example, electrospinning has been used for this purpose, in which hydroxyapatite nanoparticles were utilized [34-36].

Figure 1- possible strategies to use nanoparticles in the production of bioactive materials: (a) nanocomposites based on the fabrication of nano-fibers; (b) spatial control of nanoparticles in the production of patterned bioactive surfaces; (c) bioactive multilayered coatings produced by layer-by-layer; (d) polymer-based scaffolds; (e) hydrogels or solid bioactive biomaterials.

Nanoparticles can also be deposited onto surfaces. The spatial control of the regions where the nanoparticles are dispersed may produce patterned bioactive surfaces (Fig. 1b). Moreover, we can also control the deposition of nanoparticles on surfaces in which the coating thickness may be controlled, using, for example layer-by-layer technology (Fig. 1c). Such methodology has been used to produce multilayered organic-inorganic composite films that included bioactive glass nanoparticles [37]. The obtained bioactive coatings tried to mimic the ordered brick-and-mortar arrangement found in the microstructure of seashell nacre, known for its superior hardness, strength and toughness [38]. Nanoparticles can also be included in 3D composite materials as one may improve the final mechanical properties as compared with the use of larger particles. Bioactive nanoparticles may be included, for example in scaffolds (Fig. 1d); for example, poly(L-lactic acid)-based scaffolds containing bioactive glass nanoparticles, induced the precipitation of apatite onto the surface of the pores upon immersion of SBF [39]. Non-porous materials including nanoparticles in the form of gels or hard devices may also be produced (Fig. 1e). As an example, chitosan- β -glycerophosphate salt formulation with bioactive glass nanoparticles was conceived to prepare novel thermo-responsive hydrogels exhibiting a bioactive character [40]. Such systems are liquid at room temperature and turn to a gel at body temperature, being thus adequate to be used as an injectable system. The use of nanoparticles in this context facilitates the introduction of the liquid in situ through a minimally invasive procedure.

FABRICATION OF BIOACTIVE NANOPARTICLES USING SOL-GEL METHODOLOGIES

The bioactive glass-ceramic nanoparticles (nBGC) that have been used in our research group are from the ternary system $\text{SiO}_2\text{-CaO-P}_2\text{O}_5$, in which different composition have been tested (see, for example, [41]). The preparation method could be briefly described as follows: a given quantity of $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is dissolved in water at room temperature; a tetraethoxysilane (TEOS)-ethanol is prepared and added to the calcium nitrate solution; the pH of the solution is adjusted to 1-2 using citric acid;

the reaction mixture is kept stirring until an homogeneous and transparent solution is obtained; the solution is dropped into a large quantity of ammoniated deionized water in which ammonium dibasic phosphate was dissolved in advance; during the dripping process the pH value is maintained at around 11 by successive addition of ammonium hydroxide solution; after stirring during several hours (for example, 48 hours) and resting for 24 hours the precipitate is separated by centrifugation, washed with deionized water and finally separated in a 2% PEG-water solution; the precipitation is freeze dried followed by a calcinations step.

Figure 2 – Field emission scanning electron microscopy image showing rice-shaped bioactive glass-ceramic nanoparticles, based on the results from ref. [42]. The false colours allow to distinguish better the prepared material. The author thanks Dr. Z. Hong to provide this image.

Based on the procedure used, nanoparticles may be obtained with different sizes, and even with different geometries. For example, Figure 2 shows an example of rice-shaped or claviform nBGCs with a low silicon content produced by an improved sol-gel method, which is in sizes of about 70 nm in diameter and 210 nm in length [42]. Calcination at 700 °C did not destroy the global protuberances on the surface of the nanoparticles. Such a coarse texture can improve the specific surface area of nano-particles and facilitate the resolvability of the BAC material, increasing its bioactivity. If combined with biocompatible polymers, the rough surface of the nanofiller, combined with its anisotropy, is expected to increase the interface strength between the BAC particles and the polymer matrix. *In vitro* bioactivity tests showed that these novel bioactive nanoparticles containing small quantity of silicon have excellent biomineralization capability. Such osteoconductive nanoparticles may find applications in the biomedical area, including in tissue engineering of mineralized tissues or in others orthopedic applications.

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